

From Traditional Public Administration To Digital Hybrid Public Administration

Alper Tunga ŞEN.¹ 0000-0003-1943-9040
 Kastamonu University, Türkiye, alpertungasen@gmail.com

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Abstract

When the process from past to present is examined, it can be seen that digitalization and technology are increasingly making themselves felt in daily life. This digitalization and technology not only causes many innovations in every field, but also causes many changes in the field of public administration. On the other hand, with the effects of this change, public administration is increasingly gaining a hybrid structure. Many different studies argue that the digital public management approach and the hybrid public management approach are different from each other. The purpose of this study is to reveal that the hybrid structure of today's public administration approach is actually realized together with digitalization. In addition, it is emphasized that today's public administration approach should actually be called a digital hybrid public administration approach. The study was carried out by the literature review method, and the works of many local and foreign scientists were examined. As a result, it is understood that today's public administration approach should be described as digital hybrid public administration. It is also important as it is a study that can be expanded with field research in the future.

Keywords: Public Administration, Hybrid, Digitalization, Technology

1. Introduction

In the aftermath of rapid global changes, particularly evident in the 21st century, public administration has found itself in a process-oriented differentiation (Ksumasari et al., 2023). The continuity of these global change movements in the public sector has not been strongly criticized by scholars, given the widespread transformations worldwide (Aristovnik et al., 2022). This study thoroughly examines the consequences of these change movements in the field of public administration and subsequently delves into how public administration has taken shape in the new hybrid world.

Modern state structures today reveal that the public sector is not profit-driven; instead, its aim is to provide effective and efficient services to the public. However, it should not be overlooked that non-profit public organizations increasingly express changing ideas, thoughts, and demands (Christensen and Legreid, 2010). While public organizations exist to meet various physical and social needs of contemporary societies, they also grapple with numerous challenges, including political, social, and economic changes over the years, the need for transformations to adapt to the environment, changing individual needs and demands, and the desire for faster access to services with the increasing speed of information flow and globalization, among others.

In the past, public administration was primarily associated with bureaucracy. However, in the present day, public administration has transformed into a unique decision-making mechanism that effectively utilizes innovations, reform movements, and technology to achieve desired goals (Ksumasari et al., 2023). This understanding of public administration did not emerge suddenly; rather, it evolved through various transformations to adapt to the changing environment, often facilitated by conflicting elements within the field

¹ Corresponding Author alpertungasen@gmail.com

(Iacovino et al., 2017). Public sector organizations, influenced by these conflicting elements such as demands, ideas, and cultural structures, have increasingly diverged from traditional and new public administration approaches, tending towards a more hybrid structure. This period of divergence has given rise to a new, not yet explicitly named understanding of public administration that implements change movements more rapidly (Lynn, 2006).

To better comprehend the development process of public administration and highlight the emphasized aspects of changes, this study categorizes the evolution of public administration into three periods: traditional public administration, new public administration, and hybrid public administration. The fundamental reasons for these changes in public administration include countries experiencing rapid technological advancements, the world population growing rapidly, rendering existing public administration approaches insufficient in addressing problems, the adoption of new management policies, and the inadequacy of public administration approaches in dealing with unforeseeable problems (Ansell et al., 2021). Consequently, public administration has continuously endeavored to adapt to this dynamic structure, aiming to enhance both productivity and efficiency through various new avenues (Sorensen and Torfing, 2021).

This study aims to elucidate the changes in the understanding of public administration and provide a better understanding of the hybrid public administration that emerges as a result of these change movements. While scholars acknowledge that the understanding of public administration approaches is becoming increasingly complex, there is a notable lack of emphasis on the distinctive features of the emerging hybrid and increasingly digitized public administration approach. Consequently, the study initially addresses the transition from traditional to new public administration. Subsequently, it extensively examines the globally accepted new hybrid world order and the concept of hybridization. The study then focuses on the processes of digitization and hybridization in public administration, exploring the goals and characteristics of the digitized and hybridized understanding of public administration.

Given that public administration approaches do not undergo rapid changes overnight but rather emerge from prolonged changes over the years, this study, theoretically, serves as an exploratory work. By incorporating scientific studies related to the topic in the literature, it becomes evident that the hybridization concept in public administration, particularly in tandem with digitization, is gaining momentum. It is essential to acknowledge that the landscape of change in public administration is continuous.

2. Transition from Traditional Public Administration Approach to New Public Administration

In order to articulate the change process more clearly within the historical context, understanding the alterations that have affected a concept is crucial. Public administration, a concept that scholars have studied for many years, is not only significant due to its inherent nature but also because it is influenced by various changes, ideological currents, and developments. Significant developments exist in many studies to comprehend the shift of public administration towards an increasingly digitized and hybrid structure. This study contends that contemporary public administration is evolving into a more digital and hybrid form. The foundation of these digitized and hybridized public administration practices is rooted in the traditional understanding of public administration, followed by the emergence of the new public administration approach worldwide. Therefore, the transition process from the traditional public administration approach to the new public administration approach is explored in the title of this study.

To understand the new public administration approach clearly, it is essential to know what the traditional public administration approach is and what elements it encompasses. Scholars have conducted studies on the traditional public administration approach for many years but have not reached a consensus on a common definition. However, there are elements that make the traditional public administration approach appear as a guiding set of ideas or a normative model. These elements can be listed as follows (Mülazımoğlu and Günel, 2023; Denhardt and Denhardt, 2000):

- Traditional public administration values neutrality while placing importance on the concept of competence. According to this approach, the state provides services directly through public institutions.
- The central focus of traditional public administration is the direct provision of public services by the state. The fundamental organizational structure for this is central bureaucracy.
- According to the traditional public administration approach, the primary duty of public administrators is to implement existing public policies. It implies that public administrators are not actively involved in policy formulation or governance activities. The priority for public administrators is the effective implementation of public goals.
- Another aspect among the principles of traditional public administration is the relationship between elected and appointed officials. Appointed officials have limited discretion in providing public services, and they have responsibilities towards elected officials.
- In the process of creating relevant programs, the control mechanism is applied from top to bottom, and individual decision-making and discretionary powers are restricted as much as possible.
- Traditional public administration advocates for a closed system to ensure the flawless functioning of the entire system, emphasizing limited citizen participation.
- Finally, tasks assigned to public administrators include planning, organizing, staffing, directing, coordinating, reporting, and budgeting.

This administrative approach is also referred to as the Weberian Bureaucracy Model and has been preferred by states in their management activities for many years (Aristovnik et al., 2022). The traditional public administration approach has highlighted several important points, such as the clear distinction between political and administrative functions, the importance of neutrality, and the anonymity of public services (Bourgon, 2007). During the period when the traditional public administration approach was adopted by states, it gained more supporters as states relatively successfully overcome challenges such as World War I, the Great Depression of 1929, and World War II (Bryson et al., 2014). However, as advocates of the approach increased, so did the criticisms from scholars who began to question its effectiveness, particularly in revealing internal operations of organizations in the public sector, personnel management, organization of institutions, and addressing growing concerns in the public sector (Gray and Jenkins, 1995). Utilizing competencies to their full extent and resolving fundamental problems underlying issues rather than addressing the problems that arise have become crucial for organizational success (Zehir, 2023). Indeed, the 1970s can be considered the years when complaints about the traditional public administration approach increased significantly. The intellectual characteristics of the approach started to lose ground, and schools related to public administration began to emphasize change discourses. By the late 1970s, the United States and the United Kingdom, as two major countries, introduced new approaches to public administration, emphasizing the need to restructure the understanding of public administration (Eryılmaz, 2019). Another influential factor in the emergence of these approaches was the deterioration of traditional bureaucratic principles in states, the increasing role of the economy in public administration approaches, and the need for a more inclusive system (Hood, 1991). In the late 1970s, the ideas that states should expand their areas of activity, calls for downsizing states, increased market liberalization, the need for more competition in public institutions, the necessity of deregulation, the differentiation of roles undertaken by public administrators, and the need for them to take on a more entrepreneurial role emerged as significant aspects and were among the first important principles of the New Public Management approach (Mülazımoğlu and Günal, 2023).

Following Hood's (1991) study, the principles laid out to enhance the efficiency and effectiveness of public administration led to the emergence of the New Public Management approach. There are seven principles in Hood's new management strategy. These include advocating for professional management in the public sector, increasing transparency, the necessity of performance metrics, giving more importance to output control,

conducting individual assessments in the public sector, increasing competition in the public sphere, and implementing accountability (Funck and Karlsson, 2020).

The New Public Management approach has been observed to emerge based on the specified characteristics and has led to significant changes in the traditional public administration approach. On the other hand, the New Public Management approach has resulted in positive changes in the practices of states. While the approach may not have provided solutions to all the problems in the public sector, scholars agree that it has presented significant solutions to the problems it addressed (Denhardt and Denhardt, 2015). Table 1 clearly articulates the aspects in which the New Public Management approach differs from the traditional public administration approach.

Table 1. Differences Between Traditional Public Management and New Public Management

	Traditional Public Administration	New Public Management
The process	Strict hierarchical management	Flexible hierarchical management
Structure	Centralist	Decentralized
Organizational Dimension	Large scale structure	Minimal scale structure
Environmental Understanding	Wide center, narrow periphery approach	Narrow center, wide periphery understanding
Tendency	Bureaucracy focused	Market oriented
Citizen's Perspective	Citizen	Customer
Mentality	Administration	Business (Management)
Administrative structure	Management based on referral and administration	Governance-based management
Quality of the State	Service state approach	Minimal state concept
Role of the state	Paternalistic leader role	Empowering leader role
Duty of the State	Rowing state	The state that steers/steers
Basis of Measurement	Input and process oriented	Output and result oriented
Fee	Fixed fee management	Performance based pay
Normative Order	Command and control oriented	Focused on negotiation and persuasion
Values	Productivity	Effectiveness and efficiency
Control	Rules-based auditing	Performance-related audit

(Source: Ozan ve Yolcu, 2021)

As seen in Table 1, significant differences between the traditional public administration approach and the new public administration approach have been highlighted, to the extent that the understanding of public administration has been relatively redefined. This approach, adopted by OECD countries in recent years, has gained popularity, leading states to integrate new public administration approaches into their existing public administration systems (Hood, 1995).

The increasing efforts of more countries to integrate the new public administration approach into their public administration systems have resulted in both successful and unsuccessful outcomes. Firstly, a concept termed as "managerialism" has emerged with the new public administration approach. This concept can be characterized as encouraging treating citizens more like customers, signifying the transfer of private sector management activities to the public sector (Pollitt, 1990). Another criticism is that the new approach seemingly encourages public administrators to act like entrepreneurs, which has strengthened the dichotomy between politics and administration. This, in turn, poses a serious threat to public ethics (Kaboolian, 1998). In addition

to public ethics, concerns have arisen regarding democracy, accountability, and scrutinizability, raising ethical issues (Dunleavy and Hood, 1994). Lastly, another criticism is that the implementation of the new public administration approach has led to a reduction in budgets allocated to essential public services such as health and education at the expense of quality standards (Larbi, 1999).

These critiques, identified through various studies conducted by many scholars, have led the new public administration approach to adopt missions that involve multiple areas, such as social justice, equality, and protection of rights, in order to address and alleviate concerns. Indeed, the absence of the same problems in all countries where the new public administration approach is implemented suggests that the approach is not entirely flawed; rather, it implies that countries have not adapted the new approach according to their own public administration traditions. For example, in African countries, corruption has been prevented through autonomous tax institutions, but irregularities have been observed in public services provided through contracts. Another example is the efforts made in the United Kingdom to increase accountability, which did not yield the desired results (Mülazımoğlu and Günal, 2023).

In a general assessment, with the new public administration approach, countries and their public organizations have emphasized a more specialized understanding in developing their cultures (Christensen and Legreid, 2010). The emergence of the new public administration approach can be considered the most significant factor in the increase of shortcomings in traditional public administration and its inadequacy in solving global problems. When considered both theoretically and practically, the new public administration approach has brought about a new breath in public administration, fostering the belief that innovative practices rather than traditional methods can better address existing problems (Mülazımoğlu and Günal, 2023). However, it is crucial to consider the criticisms made against the new public administration, especially the need for an innovative approach in the public sector following this approach. In this regard, the search for new systems and methods in the public sector continues. Over time, the implementation of these new methods and systems leads to paradigm shifts in public administration (Soetanto et al., 2020).

Today, this paradigm shift has become evident with the increasing use of technology, where traditional and new approaches are used together in public administration. The change in methods preferred by states to meet public services, the integration of technology into the public sector, and the simultaneous preference for effective principles in public administration approaches have led to both an increasing digitization and a shift towards a more hybrid structure in public administration. Therefore, the next subsection of the study discusses the process of digitization and hybridization in public administration, and the reasons for the emergence of the digital hybrid public administration approach are identified. It is essential to note that the digitized hybrid public administration approach does not have an entirely different identity; rather, it only differs in its focal points. As mentioned in the previous sections, hybridization involves adding to existing systems to create new or updated mixed systems. The next subsection of the study delves into how the process of digitization and hybridization in public administration emerged, providing a detailed understanding of the foundations of the digitized and hybrid public administration approach.

3. The New Hybrid World (Digitalization and Hybridization in Governance)

Before delving into the process of hybridization and digitization in public administration in this study, it is essential to explore how these two concepts are defined in the literature. The increasing integration of technology into daily life worldwide, the rapid dissemination of information, and individuals' faster access to information have led to significant changes in management activities, as in many other areas. As mentioned in the previous section of the study, the concept of change has been evident since the dawn of humanity, and one of the primary reasons for this is that the only constant is change itself. As in every field, scientists closely monitor changes in management science, conducting studies on what changes need to be made where classical systems fall short.

In the present day, the most significant factor triggering change is the concept of digitization, which is one of the necessities of the digital age. Explaining digitization in this section of the study contributes to a better understanding of the digital and hybrid public administration approach.

Digitization should not be considered a temporary factor worldwide. It should be regarded as a versatile development that influences many sectors and areas today. Both the private and public sectors are among the sectors shaped by this technological change. Essentially, digitization implies the digital connection of individuals and institutions. The digital transformation through platforms, websites, social media, artificial intelligence (AI), and connected devices has led to "datification," speeding up various processes and increasing efficiency (Endres et al., 2019; Gupta and George, 2016; Di Vaio and Varriale, 2020). This process, initiated by the preference for these tools, has profoundly changed how digital technologies operate within sectors over the past two decades (Gray et al., 2013). Companies producing both goods and services within the sector are transforming not only as a way to rethink what their customers like but also digitally (Galati and Galati, 2019). This transformation with digitization results in the emergence of new management models (Berman, 2012). For instance, organizations and businesses, with the advent of digitization, have had the chance to strengthen their decision-making mechanisms, accountability, and relationships with various social actors. Social media platforms, in particular, play a significant role in this context. With these platforms, organizations can now rapidly obtain instant feedback, a process that was challenging in the past. The rapid development of digital technologies has become a fundamental reason for change in the field of management, as in all areas. However, the transformation in management should not be solely associated with technology, as mentioned in the previous section. The decrease in the popularity of the traditional management approach and the subsequent adoption of new management practices were influenced by various global adversities (economic crises, wars, etc.).

Today, management approaches continue to change, increasingly forming a series of activities that are built upon one another. It is at this point that the concept of hybridization has become a frequent choice in the literature. The hybridization process can be defined as combining different elements of two basic structures into a single common model. As a result of hybridization, complex combinations of various activities such as products, services, and cost structures are presented more effectively and efficiently. A hybrid model becomes nearly perfect with these combinations and increases its capacity to adapt to ever-growing expectations (Brown, 2008). In other words, hybridization is also referred to as "mixing" in the literature. According to another definition, hybridization is described as the separation of existing forms in a structure from current practices and their reintegration with new forms in new applications (Rowe and Schelling, 1991). When considering both definitions, hybridization goes beyond being a valid concept for a single aspect. Especially, the second definition made encompasses a wide structure that explains the change in structural forms of social organization (Pieterse, 1993). Considering the explanations, hybridization implies not the complete alteration of an existing structure but rather the integration of two structures, referred to as old and new, to create a more effective and efficient new structure. In fact, the world's increasing preference for hybrid business models, hybrid management models, and hybrid applications is one of the reasons for this. Achieving a more effective and efficient structure.

With the more effective influence of globalization and digitization, both macro and micro structures have been connected more harmoniously through information networks. The element of management, like in the economy and politics, has also gained an increasingly computational structure (Ulusoy and Şen, 2019). This new management structure has led to the emergence of a hybrid management approach, bringing together both digitization and the effective activities of management throughout historical processes (Boyalı, 2023). This situation was particularly evident during the pandemic period, which emerged at the beginning of 2020 and was felt most profoundly worldwide. The recommendation for people to stay at home during that period significantly affected both work and education. In response to overcoming this negative situation, hybrid

working and educational models that better utilize the possibilities of digitization and technology were implemented.

The models used are the result of integration between existing practices, as defined in the hybridization concept, rather than the emergence of a new application. Initially preferred by the private sector and educational institutions, digital and hybrid management activities subsequently led to a significant demand in the public sector. This ongoing change, which decision-makers cannot ignore, reveals the manifestation of digitization and hybridization in public administration. Another crucial point not to be forgotten here is that one of the most significant tools of the hybridization process is digitization. For this reason, in this study, digital public administration and hybrid public administration approaches are not treated separately; instead, the features of the digitized hybrid public administration approach are explained as a single approach. Ultimately, it is observed that the innovations brought by the digital age have led to the emergence of the hybrid public administration approach.

4. Hybridization and Digitalization Process in Public Administration

Before discussing the fundamentals of the digital hybrid public administration approach, it is crucial to mention the processes in public administration practices after which this approach was adopted. The study emphasizes that traditional public administration underwent a significant paradigm shift, transforming into the new public administration approach. It's essential to note that the transformation of the new public administration approach into the digital hybrid public administration approach is not essentially an approach where all features are completely renewed. The key to this transformation is, in fact, the development of public administration approaches with digitization. It signifies the transformation of existing practices in public administration with digitization and hybridization.

In the public sector, hybridization can have different meanings, especially in organizational structures where both structural and cultural dimensions coexist. On the other hand, hybrid public structures also refer to semi-governmental structures (Lan and Rainey, 1992). The concept of the hybrid world was first introduced in the literature by Emery and Giaque (2014) in the book "The Hybrid Universe of Public Management in the 21st Century." The authors defined hybrid structures as political and administrative structures offering alternatives to the existing public environment (Marchand and Brunet, 2019).

There are several reasons why public administration has a hybrid structure, as stated by many scholars. These reasons provide insights into the process. Firstly, the increasing integration of new technological developments into daily life is the most important factor in the growing discussion of the digital hybrid public administration approach. This leads to increased opportunities and facilitation of life, attracting attention (Baldys and Piatek, 2017). Another significant reason is the shift in interest from physical environments to virtual environments, leading to the emergence of new working principles in public administration. For instance, the global pandemic has resulted in the creation of more comfortable, efficient working conditions such as remote work, distance learning, virtual interviews, etc. (Ford et al., 2021). Thirdly, collaboration activities have gained importance as a result of globalization. Collaboration between institutions involved in public administration approaches has now turned into an understanding that increases shared working areas. The digital hybrid public administration approach is crucial in promoting and supporting collaborations both among public institutions and between the public and private sectors (Abdou, 2021).

As can be seen from these reasons, digitalization is vital in public administration because it allows information to be processed, stored and shared efficiently. Digitalization not only increases the efficiency of public administration, but also increases transparency and accountability. By streamlining processes and reducing paperwork, digitalization allows public administrators to allocate their time and resources more effectively, ultimately leading to better service delivery to citizens. Additionally, digitalization enables the implementation of data-based decision-making processes, ensuring that policies and programs are based on

accurate and up-to-date information. Additionally, it can empower citizens by providing easier access to government services and information (Ciancarini vd., 2024). Individuals can interact with government institutions, access important documents and participate in decision-making processes more easily through online platforms and digital interfaces. This can contribute to a more inclusive and participatory democracy in which citizens feel more connected to the government and are better informed about its activities. Moreover, digitalization can provide cost savings for public administrations as it can streamline operations, reduce redundancies and minimize the need for physical infrastructure. By adopting digital solutions, public administrations can also support environmental sustainability by reducing paper use and energy consumption (Leao and Canedo, 2018).

Especially during periods when the new public administration approach is preferred, problems arise in centrally planned policies, the distribution of managerial tasks, and the enhancement of innovation in the public sector. Additionally, crises such as natural disasters, pandemics, and large-scale irregular migrations reveal serious inadequacies in public sector activities, subjecting public administrators to substantial criticism. These criticisms and problems have led to an increasing need for numerical data that would allow a better understanding of public administration. These numerical data are becoming increasingly available at extraordinary speeds through digitization. The most significant contribution of this data is undoubtedly the enhancement of efficiency and productivity in public administration (Boyalı, 2023).

Considering the advocates of the new public administration approach, it is understood that the new public administration approach is based on combining market and management theories. On the other hand, the new public administration approach has been criticized for its economic uncertainties and contradictions. Even with these criticisms, some scholars argue that the new public administration approach is also a hybrid approach (Christensen and Legreid, 2010).

The hybridization of public administration approaches actually began to emerge with technological developments known as the fourth industrial revolution and digitalization initiatives. Technological developments, coupled with digitization, have increased the emphasis on the need for innovations in public services, increased collaboration, and enhanced creativity (Emery and Giauque, 2014). Technological developments and the increase in digitization are causing a change in the understanding of public administration, leading to a gradual transformation of the new public administration approach. The foundation of the study manifests itself precisely at this point. The digitization brought about by contemporary technology and the innovations brought by the era are causing the new public administration approach to change and gradually acquire a more hybrid structure. Thus, the current public administration approach can be described not as an entirely new approach but rather as a hybrid structure that combines public administration approaches with digitization.

In the hybrid age within the public sector, increasing benefits are being derived from technology and digitization. In the concept of the new hybrid world, public administration primarily adopts an understanding that focuses on who the participants or stakeholders are, the contribution to the process if public needs are met, the extent to which institutions within the public sector can use technology, how contributions can be made for development, and how analytical and predictive capabilities can be improved (Ksumasari et al., 2023). Considering all these aspects, the changing nature of public administration, highlighted by the digital and hybrid public administration approach, is addressed in various principles in the next section of the study.

5. Digital and Hybrid Public Administration Approach

As a result of the high-speed digitization and the gradual hybridization of systems worldwide, different alternatives are emerging both in political and administrative aspects. One of these areas can be characterized as public administration approaches (Ksumasari et al., 2023). The modernization process of public administration approaches can primarily be described as efforts to enhance the quality of management and

governance activities, and to redefine the structures, tasks, and responsibilities of state entities and public institutions (Virant, 2009). In this study, public administration approaches are discussed in three periods: Traditional Public Administration Approach, New Public Administration Approach, and Digital Hybrid Public Administration Approach. The first two approaches have been detailed under previous headings, and under this heading, the focus is on the perspective and tools of the digital hybrid public administration approach towards elements of public administration. It is crucial to note here that, despite some previous studies examining the concepts of digital public administration and hybrid public administration separately, the most influential factor in the hybridization of public administration approaches is, in fact, digitization. Therefore, these two perspectives should be considered under a single approach.

The main outlines and distinctions of the digital hybrid public administration approach are presented in Table 2.

Table 2. Digital Hybrid Public Administration Model

Fundamentals	Digital Hybrid Public Administration Model
Basic Claim	It emphasizes a more effective and holistic understanding in technological terms. In addition, it emphasizes a management approach in which many different actors come together, unified governance and comprehensive digitalization.
Relevant Period	The concept of digitalization in public administration gained momentum in 2005, and the concept of hybridization gained momentum after the last pandemic, but both continue today in an integrated manner.
Principles	Holism, digitalization, citizen-oriented, sustainable and constantly active relations, continuous integration, participation-oriented, sectoral unification and cooperation.
Role of the State	A collaborative state approach prevails at all levels of management, emphasizing participation through all kinds of electronic channels and digitalization, and including all actors in the management process.
Employee's Role	It acts as a conciliator and mediator, providing fast service delivery with the help of electronic media.
Role of the Citizen	He/she is involved in decision-making mechanisms in an interactive manner, and plays the role of co-decision maker and problem-solving aid.
Organizational Structure	Organizational structures where the understanding of harmony and integrity prevails and benefit from technologies such as smart systems and information technologies are supported. Organizations are also expected to attach importance to restructuring processes.
Management Culture	A transparent understanding of the state that contributes to society and creates public value prevails.
Possible Problems	These can be listed as deficiencies in both theoretical and practical knowledge regarding the development of technology, increasing security fears as a result of digitalization and hybridization, and increasing control fears of states.

(Source: Aristovnik vd., 2022)

When considering the principles mentioned in the digital hybrid public administration approach, it signifies both a hybrid structure borrowing different values and principles from past public administration approaches and a digital structure in terms of bringing together technology and public administration (Ksumasari et al., 2023). The digital hybrid public administration approach expects interactive citizenship, urging individuals to concurrently fulfill their citizenship duties and control duties, thus developing solutions to problems (Chen et al., 2020).

Another noteworthy point not mentioned in Table 2 but requiring attention is the reconsideration of the leadership concept after the adoption of the digital hybrid public administration approach. The dynamic process of change in the public sector shows an increase in the acceptance rates of individuals who can generate solutions to problems more quickly as leaders. With the digital hybrid public administration approach, the

expected characteristics of leaders are changing. Leaders, who were previously expected to be charismatic, directive, and relational, must now adapt to time, digitization, and the challenges brought by technology (McMullin and Raggio, 2020; Kelly, 2019). Leaders of this era are also referred to as digital leaders (Raharja et al., 2019).

The Digital Hybrid Public Administration approach, emerging after the New Public Administration approach, can be interpreted as an understanding that transforms the features of the existing New Public Administration reforms into a more hybrid structure. When these hybrid structure principles are considered, there is an emphasis on a more collaborative and integrated structure (Christensen and Legreid, 2010). This situation indicates that, in an era becoming increasingly digitalized and hybridized, the dynamics of the public and its environment have not changed significantly, but adaptation to new principles is required. The Digital Hybrid Public Administration approach emerges as a hybrid structure with the addition of digital elements to public administration dynamics. This approach particularly highlights the importance of innovation in the present day and emphasizes the need for increased collaboration and creativity (Ksumasari et al., 2023).

The expression of the principles of the digital hybrid public administration approach does not imply that there are no concerns associated with the approach. Firstly, the change in the understanding of public administration has led to conflicts between various structures and elements. This conflicting structure is criticized due to making the public administration system more complex and challenging to understand. Additionally, both individuals and states express concerns about the security issues that digitization may create, raising worries about privacy violations. Another concern regarding the new approach is the potential for states to use increased control powers with digitization. This concern, especially among citizens, creates serious concerns and brings more attention to the violation of privacy in private life. Finally, there are concerns that a lack of sufficient knowledge about technology and digitization may cause problems in practice (Aristovnik et al., 2022; Ksumasari et al., 2023).

Throughout history, it has been known that individuals who are open to innovation are fewer compared to those resistant to innovations. Therefore, it is natural for potential problems created by a new approach to be highlighted. Identifying concerns and anxieties related to the digital hybrid public administration approach before they turn into problems is crucial for the effective implementation of the approach. Taking necessary measures for the more efficient operation of the digital hybrid public administration approach, establishing solid theoretical and practical foundations for digitization, plays a significant role in overcoming potential challenges in public administration.

6. Conclusion

Considering the information presented throughout the study, it can be observed that the current understanding of public administration is essentially a blend of past approaches. Over the last two decades, digitization has been increasing worldwide, and the dynamics of society have been changing rapidly. Developments in public administration have a long history, and global developments have made it imperative for public administration to adapt to changes. In the historical process, the changes in public administration can be categorized as traditional public administration approach, new public administration approach, and digital hybrid public administration approach. The concept of public administration has been significantly influenced by these changing processes. Each of the mentioned models, preferred by authorities, has been introduced into the literature by building upon the previous approach and developing solutions to the problems arising in the previous approach with new developments.

In recent decades, public organizations have undergone a significant transformation in response to the evolving social, economic, and political contexts of our postindustrial society. This transformation has led to public organizations becoming increasingly complex and hybrid, as they face various ideas, considerations, demands, structures, and cultural elements. The transition to a digital and hybrid structure in public

administration has been seen as a solution to the challenges faced by traditional bureaucracies. However, the transition to a digital and hybrid structure in public administration has not been sufficient to solve all the problems (Kariuki & Tshandu, 2015).

The essence of the study is to conceptualize the digital hybrid public administration model and identify the principles that digital hybrid public administration should adhere to. Additionally, it aims to demonstrate that the digital public administration approach and the hybrid public administration approach have evolved together. Especially in recent years, technology, which has become intertwined with public administration, has become one of the fundamental tools used to address the problems arising from global pandemics and crises. Therefore, it is not accurate to characterize the accepted approach to public administration today as merely a blend of previous approaches. The public administration practices preferred today have become more effective and interactive structures with the advancement of technology. Furthermore, the increased use of information technologies in public administration activities, the changing definition of leadership, the growing importance of data sets, and the emphasis on innovation and speed in public services can be considered among the contributions of the digital age to public administration.

In addition, digital hybrid public management aims to be an approach that combines elements of traditional public management with new public management principles. This innovative approach aimed to leverage the strengths of both traditional and new public management to increase the effectiveness and efficiency of public services. Digital hybrid public management aims to create a balanced and adaptable framework for tackling complex public sector challenges by integrating the hierarchy and stability of traditional public management with the customer-focused and performance-oriented aspects of new public management. This approach emphasizes the importance of accountability, transparency and citizen participation, while also encouraging innovation and flexibility in service delivery. Digital hybrid public management seeks to optimize resource allocation and improve the overall quality of public service delivery by using a wide range of tools and techniques, including data-driven decision-making and collaborative governance. This approach has made a name for itself as an approach that achieves most of these, even if it cannot fully provide them today (Li, 2022). Even though it can be seen that many of its shortcomings have been eliminated in this way, it should not be forgotten that there are critical aspects of the approach. These criticized aspects continue to be renewed by scientists in order to create a better approach.

All these reasons indicate that the concept of hybrid public administration is not merely the combination of approaches. In addition, the hybrid public administration approach has evolved into an approach that combines digital age opportunities with previous practices. Therefore, digitization and hybridization are among the most important descriptors of contemporary public administration. It seems appropriate to refer to the approach preferred by many states today as the 'Digital Hybrid Public Administration Approach'.

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